

Culture-Based Leadership Development

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ABSTRACT

The pattern of leadership is an important factor in advancing leadership. The degradation of Cultural values as a result of modernization are a barrier to establishing cultural leadership. One of the challenge is the electoral system, as is the reliance on ancestor involvement. For cultural leadership patterns, dynastic and authoritarian leadership are at the forefront. The purpose of this study is to promote the development of cultural leadership. According to the findings, adjustments to leadership style are critical; the development of culture-based leadership too entails the ability to modify leadership styles that are consistent with current cultural norms and rules. Direct and open communication reduces conflict and improves artistic performance. Cultural leaders are carried on over generations, from parents to children, ancestors, and Birthright.

INTRODUCTION

The character to be formed is the product of the fundamental principles contained in the instructions of Pancasila and the daily values that develop in a civilized society. By using character building, each student can expand leadership, responsibility, honesty, creativity, and culture so that character building goals can be achieved optimally (Giri, 2020). The relationship between the principal's leadership and teacher performance has important relevance to student personality (Ilham et al., 2021).

Local governance is best understood here as qualities that emerge from local contexts, histories, institutions, cultures, and power relations (Vasstrøm & Normann, 2019). The characteristics of local wisdom-based organizational culture developed in schools include: child-friendly school-based women's leadership, dual roles as teachers, strong work ethic, and religion (Imam Junaris et al., 2022).

The importance of organizational culture to strengthen green practices in the workplace (Bulińska-Stangrecka & Bagieńska, 2021). Leadership styles and organizational performance have been developed using human resource management strategies such as development, motivation, enforcement, and transfer (Khalil et al., 2022). Spiritual leadership has a strong impact on organizational commitment and productivity, vocation and membership seem to be better mediators in the relationship between spiritual leadership and organizational commitment and productivity (Usman et al., 2019). Education unit leaders have guided and nurtured employees with full sincerity in improving their performance (Herman et al., 2022). The current trends in the topic of cultural leadership in the last three years can be explained in the figure below:

Figure 1. Cultural Leadership Topic Trends
source: Google Trends, 2023

Decision makers must take into account (mandatory) the cultural basis of subordinates when choosing the best alternative to solve organizational problems (Iancu & Badea, 2020). Value-based leadership is challenged to be created within companies, churches, and governing bodies a culture of expectation imbued with a sense of civility, honesty, and integrity (Hester,

2019). The three most common representations of professional leadership culture include widespread collaboration among professionals, a culture of trust, and a supportive environment (Liggett, 2022).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The dominant leadership of ethical and intellectual thought in many western countries hinders progress (Summerfield & Dai, 2020). The traditional deficit treatment model leads to an approach that focuses on strengths and relational ways of being a leader (Hubley et al., 2022). Servant and transcendental leadership are the same focus on the long-term relationship between leader and follower, they still affect job satisfaction partially, not simultaneously (Cahyadi et al., 2020). The leadership model "Sundanese Style Harmony" is an ideal formulation as an alternative to existing leadership models that prioritize harmony and balance between Sundanese Religion and Culture, where the position of Religion and Culture is balanced, there is nothing relatively higher or lower (Prihana et al., 2020).

Their close and consistent alignment with what ethical leaders, servant leaders, transformational leaders, and authentic leaders say and do provides evidence of why leaders choose one or more of these leadership styles successfully (Lumpkin, 2023). Development of a comprehensive model aimed at establishing a culture of internal clinical supervision to meet staff and client needs (Sewell et al., 2023). Similar organizations globally, emphasize the need to explore the generalization of these results and investigate additional moderation factors that can affect organizational culture, leadership, and performance (Tistasari, 2023). Teacher job satisfaction and increased rewards in a good organizational culture, will promote better transformational leadership. This will also improve teacher performance and better salaries. With the better performance of teachers and transformational leadership, it will also improve the quality of work done by teachers (Harahap et al., 2019).

Employee perceptions of various individual, group and organizational factors support employee values and beliefs about knowledge processes (Intezari et al., 2022). In general, people pay less attention to leadership from cultural elements. Misunderstandings due to language problems, different communication methods and different value orientations of people from different cultural backgrounds. This research will examine leadership development based on local culture. One of the weaknesses in the application of local culture is the shift in cultural values. The community is no longer fixated on decisions based on consensus.

Figure 1. Leader Competency Relationship

METHODOLOGY

The research method used is qualitative using a phenomenological approach. The researchers chose phenomenological methods to investigate the situation on the ground. In the study of phenomenology, human experience is analyzed through detailed descriptions of the individual under study. According to Rudestan and Newton, the center of attention in phenomenological research focuses on individual experiences in a particular context. Briefly, researchers will try to describe what they find behind a person's appearance regarding their experience (Subagyo, 2014). Phenomenology is a way of describing phenomena in general using a personal description style from a personal point of view. In this approach, the words single personal subject such as I or I are used (Wijaya, 2018).

Phenomenology seeks to decipher, namely: first, as a scientific approach, phenomenology can describe and explain an event as it is without changing the data contained in it. This method has the view that the object it focuses on is considered a complete entity and is not connected with other objects. This approach is concrete in a comprehensive and not partial approach so that a complete understanding of an object is obtained (Helaluddin, 2018). Data sources are the subject of reference that is used as a guide for conducting a study to take place. The sources of research data are all that can provide information about services in Lewekeleng village, Adonara, East Flores. Research data in the form of written or spoken words, images, photos or actions obtained namely *paper*,

place and *person*. Paper is the source of data documents, books, magazines or other written materials. Both in the form of theories, research reports and so on (Arikunto, 2010). Data sources in this study are primary data sources and secondary data sources 1) *Person*: Tarawanan traditional leader and Taranekin, Village Head. 2) *Place*: Adonara, East Flores. 3) *Paper*: in the form of cultural documents.

Data in qualitative research are obtained from various sources using data triangulation techniques to obtain data validity. Therefore, data collection is carried out continuously until the data reaches the desired saturation level (Sugiyono, 2013). The data processing process can be done through the steps of preparation and interpretation to form a conclusion. In an effort to interpret phenomena according to natural contexts, qualitative data collection that includes naturalistic, inductive, and holistic approaches is required. Naturalistic is an approach in which data analysis is based on actual situations that undergo changes naturally, openly, and do not involve manipulation of variables. The process of induction analysis involves the use of induction thinking procedures to reveal specific and detailed information in order to find important and unique categories, dimensions, and relationships that need to be conveyed clearly. Holistic means that the whole phenomenon must be understood by researchers as a complex system, a relationship that involves the whole and is not viewed in a way that is too simple (Suryabrata, 2018). This study applies a non-statistical qualitative analysis approach, where the process of data reduction and data presentation is carried out simultaneously with data collection after the data is collected. The three components of analysis (data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing) are interconnected

RESEARCH RESULT

In this section, you should describe each step taken to complete your research. You should not include too many descriptive statistical results here; on the other hand, it should be summarized in a more readable table or graph. You should never forget the numbers for each table and chart presented in your paper.

<u>Score</u>	<u>Criteria</u>
50,00 – 100,00	Low
100,01 – 150,00	Medium
	<u>High</u>

Table 1. Three Box Method

In this section, each statistical test you perform should be thoroughly explained. This section is very important to describe the research methodology used. Each statistical finding should be summarized and presented in a table or graph; not just copy-paste from your statistics tool.

DISCUSSION

This section allows you to describe your research findings academically. You may not enter figures related to your statistical tests here; instead, you should explain those numbers here. You should structure your discussion with academic support for your studies and a good explanation according to the specific area you are investigating.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Provide some conclusions and implementation of the research results.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

In writing this article the researcher realizes that there are still many shortcomings in terms of language, writing, and form of presentation considering the limited knowledge and abilities of the researchers themselves. Therefore, for the perfection of the article, the researcher expects constructive criticism and suggestions from various parties.

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